

Supplementary Figures 1-11 from “Identification of coding and non-coding mutational hotspots in cancer genomes” (Piraino and Furney).

Supplementary Figure 1: Log₁₀ of total mutations per genome, ordered by median mutations within each tumour type. There is considerable variation both within and between cancer types. The most highly mutated cancer types are generally associated with intense exposure to known mutational process, such as tobacco smoke in lung cancer and DNA repair defects in gastric cancer.

Supplementary Figure 2: For comparison, we show the location of mutations (black arrows) within a recurrent CTCF binding site that was highlighted in a previous analysis [28]. The mutation positions and nucleotide changes observed in our sample match those identified in this previous analysis, despite the fact that our dataset lacks any colorectal cancer samples.

Supplementary Figure 3: We show recurrence score (plotted as $\log(\text{score} + 2)$) plotted against GC content. Regions with mutations per patient > 1.2 are in orange, with recurrence score > 10 and mutations per patient ≤ 1.2 in black, and all others in purple.

Supplementary Figure 4: Recurrent *TERT* promoter mutations identified in our data set. The mutations occur at one of the previously identified bases, generating a *de novo* ETS binding site.

Supplementary Figure 5: *PLEKHS1* recurrently mutated region that has previously been identified. We identify mutations at the same base position as previous analyses.

Supplementary Figure 6: UCSC browser image depicting a recurrently mutated region identified by our method. Mutations are depicted by black arrows. This region is flanked on the left by the gene *MEDI6*. The mutations observed in this region are focused within a conserved region overlapping a region of the genome with ENCODE evidence of transcription factor binding, possibly indicating selection.

Supplementary Figure 7: Sequence logo depicting the *MEF2A* motif. Text above the logo is the reference sequence observed within the recurrently mutated region in the MED16 promoter. Mutated positions are depicted in red.

Supplementary Figure 8: UCSC browser image of a second recurrently mutated region identified by our method. Mutations are depicted by black arrows. This region overlaps a reasonably conserved intron of the gene *GPR126*. The mutations within this region occur exclusively at two nucleotides in a wholly mutually exclusive manner.

Supplementary Figure 9: Recurrently mutated region overlapping the miRNA *MIR142*. The region is highly conserved, as suggested by its inclusion among the top non-coding regions based on combined score. The mutations are spread throughout the region and occur exclusively in lymphoma samples, suggesting that this region may be a target of somatic hypermutation, not necessarily selection.

50bp window: CACTCATCCATAAAGTAGGAAACACTACACCCTCCAGTGCTGTTAGTAGTG
hsa-miR-142-5p: CATAAAGTAGAAAGCACTACT

The image shows a sequence alignment between a 50bp window and hsa-miR-142-5p. The 50bp window sequence is CACTCATCCATAAAGTAGGAAACACTACACCCTCCAGTGCTGTTAGTAGTG. The hsa-miR-142-5p sequence is CATAAAGTAGAAAGCACTACT. Mutated positions in the 50bp window are highlighted in red: the 'A' at position 10, the 'A' at position 14, the 'A' at position 15, the 'C' at position 16, and the 'C' at position 20. Black arrows point to these mutated positions: one arrow points to the red 'A' at position 10, two arrows point to the red 'A's at positions 14 and 15, one arrow points to the red 'C' at position 16, and one arrow points to the red 'C' at position 20.

Supplementary Figure 10: *MIR142* reference aligned with the sequence of mature microRNA has-miR142-5p. Mutated positions are depicted in red.

Supplementary Figure 12: UCSC browser image of a recurrently mutated region overlapping an intron of the gene *PRIM2*. Mutations are depicted as black arrows. All mutations within the region occur at one of two nucleotides and are mutually exclusive.

Supplementary Figure 13: Sequence logo depicting the *FOXP2* motif. Text above the logo is the reference sequence observed within the recurrently mutated region in the *PRIM2* intron. Mutated positions are depicted in red.

Supplementary Figure 14: UCSC browser image depicting a recurrently mutated region in an intron of the DNA repair gene *RAD51B*. This region is mutated specifically in breast cancer.